

STUDY OF COMPLEX FORMATION OF GOSSYPOL ACETIC ACID WITH CADMIUM

¹Yuldasheva M.I., ²Abdurakhmanova U.K.

¹Graduate student of the Department of Chemistry, Gulistan State University

²Doctor of Biological Sciences, professor, Gulistan State University,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14096686>

Abstract. *In the article, the effect of the multi-functionality of gossypol and its derivatives on some physico-chemical properties was analyzed, and their structure, stereochemistry and tautomerism were theoretically analyzed. Obtaining the complex of gossypol acetic acid with cadmium ion, as well as the physicochemical properties of the new substance were studied. The structure of gossypol was investigated by IR spectroscopic method, and the results were recorded when comparing the spectrum of gossypol with acetic acid.*

Keywords: *gossypol, stereochemistry, tautomerism, enantiomerism, solubility, multifunctionality, IR spectrum.*

Introduction. The migration of the analyzed element in objects and the manifestation of toxicological properties depend on the state of their combination, that is, the form of existence, and specific information about this can be found in toxicology, chemical clinic, industrial ecology, environmental chemistry, as well as pharmaceuticals, are of interest to experts at the same time.

Combined analysis methods, which include the processes of separation of substances from the inspected object and concentration of components, are promising methods and provide reliable results in the analysis of objects with complex composition.

Taking this into account, the research work devoted to studying the modification, stereochemistry and tautomerism of gossypol with metal ions is an urgent problem not only in analytical chemistry, but also in the field of organic and bioorganic chemistry.

The purpose of the research is to obtain a complex of gossypolyacetic acid with cadmium, to study its physical and chemical properties, and to study its structure by IR-spectroscopic method.

Review of literature

The use of natural compounds containing functional analytical groups can not only reduce the detection limit of the object of analysis, but also increase the reproducibility and sensitivity of the analysis method as a result of significantly reducing or completely eliminating the background effect of macrocomponents [1-4]. In natural compounds with polyfunctional groups, it allows to separate the required form of the analysis elements without changing them from other chemical modifications [5-8].

The polyfunctional structure of the molecules of gossypol and its derivatives, whose interaction reaction with cadmium ions is being studied, provides a wide range of its chemical properties. Considering this, in this study, the authors determined that its structure and composition have electron-donating properties. The structure, stereochemistry and tautomerism of atom-preserved gossypol and its derivatives were analyzed from a theoretical point of view.

Gossypol is an amorphous, crystalline, lemon-yellow colored natural biologically active substance that is soluble in various organic solvents. In addition to the presence of various polar groups in the composition of the gossypol molecule, two isopropyl groups in the naphthalene residue cause hydrophobicity. Gossypol is also very good in methyl, ethyl, isopropyl and butyl alcohols, as well as in diethylene glycol, dioxane, acetone, diethyl ether, ethyl acetate, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, dichloroethane, phenol, pyridine and heated naphthalene, heated cottonseed oil [9] dissolves well.

When studying the properties of gossypol, it is necessary to take into account the structure, stereochemistry, tautomerism and hydrogen bonds of the molecule.

Plants belonging to the *Gossipium* genus mainly contain optically inactive (+) and (-) gossypol, but (+) gossypol from cottonseeds isolated from cotton growing in some states of America isolated separately. The plant called *Thermopsis popelynia* mainly contains (+) gossypol enantiomer, whose $[\alpha]_D$ value is +4750 [10]. (+) One of the main reasons for the optical activity of gossypol is that it contains an optically active, i.e. asymmetric, carbon atom in the lactol chain, but it was found that the optical activity value of gossypol isolated from *Thermopsis popelynia* does not change when exposed to an acid solution. This does not indicate the presence of an asymmetric carbon atom, but the fact that the gossypol molecule exhibits optical activity indicates the presence of an atropisomer phenomenon.

Research methodology

To determine cadmium (II) ions from the composition of artificial compounds and minerals, its standard solution was prepared from $[\text{Cd}(\text{NO})_3]_2$ (k.t.) salt solutions. Ammonia, acetate and universal buffer mixtures, freshly prepared organic solvents (ethyl alcohol, chloroform, benzene, acetone, toluene), sulfate, hydrochloric and nitric acid solutions and alkaline solutions were also used. For transport, it was processed with ethyl alcohol, acetone, benzene (2:1:1) systems. 10% alcohol solution of sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) was controlled in iodine chambers to reveal chromatographic spots.

Continuous stirring during the reaction was carried out in a MM-5 TU 25-11834-80 magnetic stirrer. Organic solvents were removed from the system by evaporation in an IR-1M2 rotary evaporator. A lyophilic device (AutomaticFREEZE-Dryer10-010) was used for drying, and a PTP TU 25-11-1144 device was used to measure the liquid temperature of substances. The pH of the solutions was controlled by a COMBI 5000 (Germany) pH-meter. IR-spectra (FT-IR System-2000) were obtained on KBr tablets in an IR-Fourier spectrometer (Perkin-Elmer).

Preparation of solutions: To prepare a working solution of cadmium nitrate, an exact volume of salt was dissolved in distilled water, then transferred to a 250 ml volumetric flask and diluted to the mark. The initial solution of GSK was purified by dissolving an accurately weighed portion of the reagent in ethyl alcohol and recrystallized twice from an aqueous-ethanol solution beforehand. The purity of the reagent was checked by chromatography.

Initially, 25 ml of 0.1 M solutions of GSK and cadmium nitrates were taken and mixed together. The resulting mixture was stirred for 5 hours in a magnetic stirrer with an inverted refrigerator. Then the reaction mixture was removed from the solvent and the resulting product was dried in a lyophilic dryer. $R_f = 0.62$, the yield of the reaction is 71%.

Ethyl alcohol, acetone, benzene (2:1:1) systems and an iodine chamber were used to open the chromatography spots.

Analysis and results

Hydroxyl groups attached to the carbon atoms in the 1,1-position of the gossypol molecule are more reactive than the four hydroxyl groups in the 6,6- and 7,7-positions of the other carbon atoms, and the aldehyde located in the 8,8-positions due to its proximity to groups, it causes the formation of many chemical properties and hydrogen bonds unique to the gossypol molecule [12-13].

Figure 1. The formation of hydrogen bonds in the gossypol molecule. - Me: - SH3 group

Four alkyl groups in the molecule, two methyl and two isopropyl groups located in the 3,3' and 5,5' positions, respectively, make up the lipophilic part of gossypol, and the other side of the naphthalene ring occupied by hydroxyl and aldehyde groups is considered to be the lipophobic part of the molecule.

According to the authors, when extracted from the seed kernel, gossypol consists of a patchy mixture of (-) and (+) enantiomers, which can be separated from bip-bipi. The form of the (-) enantiomer is more toxic and active than the (+) enantiomer. In addition to enantiomerism, the gossypol molecule is characterized by symmetric and asymmetric tautomerism [12].

It is also noted in the literature that gossypol has two different tautomeric and conformational states in solution, and Adams and colleagues attributed most of the reactions in gossypol to its tautomerism [12-13]. The fact that gossypol has the property of polyfunctionality is due to the balance of its aldehyde-lactol (2) and benzoid-quinoid (3) states. The above considerations logically explain the reactivity of the gossypol molecule. The existing two aromatic naphthalene fragments (1), the ortho-position of two of the six hydroxyl groups to the carbonyl group and the ability to easily convert to the tautomeric state provide the uniqueness of the chemical properties and biological activity of gossypol. Formation of complex compounds with colored and heavy metal ions under certain conditions with a characteristic color is due to the presence of a functional active group [10-11].

Under certain conditions, gossypol with colored and heavy metal ions forms colored complex bipicmes. The formation of complex compounds mainly takes place due to the non-generalized pair of electrons in the hydroxyl groups attached to the hydrocarbon atoms in the 1,1' position and aldehyde groups located in the 8,8 position [10-11].

The physicochemical constants of the complex formed by acetic acid of gossypol with cadmium were studied (Table 1).

When the structure of the obtained substance was studied by the IR-spectroscopy method, it was observed that there was an interaction between GSK and the metal ion.

In the IR spectrum of the cadmium salt of gossypol, the loss of the valence vibrations of the hydroxyl groups in the region of 3510-3450 cm⁻¹ and the change in the appearance of the valence vibrations of the aldehyde group in the region of 1650-1580 cm⁻¹ show that the salt formed

by gossypol with Cd ions is the hydroxyl group of gossypol and this as well as the presence of aldehyde groups.

Table 1

Some physico-chemical quantities of gossypol acetic acid complex formed with cadmium

Chemical formula	M _r	Color	T _{suyuq} ⁰ C	R _f	Solubility
(C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₃ CHO) ₂	518	pale yellow	181-182	0.52*	Acetone, alcohol, DMFA, DMSO
Cd ₂ (C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₃ CO) ₂	742	Colorless	233-334	0,62	Water

Figure 2. Cadmium salt of Gossypol and IR spectrum of Gossypol.

Conclusions:

As a result of the interaction of gossypol acetic acid with cadmium ion, a white crystalline substance was obtained. When studying the physical and chemical properties of the obtained substance, it was observed that their properties differ from the original substances. When the structure was studied by IR spectroscopic method, it was observed that there was a change in the aldehyde group in the metal and GSK molecule and in the hydroxyl groups attached to the carbon atoms in the 1,1-position of the molecule.

REFERENCES

1. Abdurakhmanova U.K., Ettibaeva L.A., Khaidarova E.E. Extraction-photometric determination of thallium (III) 1-(2-pyridilazo)-4 hexylphenol Materialy mejdunarodnoy nauch.-technich. conf. «Science, education, production and solution of ecological problems». - Russia: Ufa, 2011. P.219-222.
2. Abdurakhmanova U.K. Extraction of gold and cerebra O, O-diamyltiofosfatom kaliya Materialy mejdunarodnoy nauch.-technich. conference "Science, education, production and solution of ecological problems". - Russia: Ufa, 2007. P.158-162.
3. Abdurakhmanova U.K., Nishonov R.A. Kolichestvennoe issledovanie kompleksov metallov, poluchennykh na osnove prirodnykh soedineniy// Vestnik GulGU.-Gulistan. - 2017. – V.1. - P.111-115.
4. Л.А.Еттибоева, У.К.Абдурахманова, А.Д.Магчанов [Изучение физико-химических свойств супрамолекулярных комплексов глицирризиновой кислоты с ментолом](#) // Universum: Химия и биология, Выпуск: 5(71). 2020. –С.35-41.
5. М.П.Мамбетмуратова, У.К.Абдурахманова Изучение физико-химических свойств комплекса глицирризиновой кислоты с кадмием // Universum: Химия и биология, Выпуск: 5(71). 2023. –С.51-55.
6. У.К.Абдурахманова, М.Р.Аскарлова, Н.Х.Якубова, М.Б.Гафурова [Спектрофотометрическое определение железа \(III\) с азопроизводными госсипола](#)// Universum: Химия и биология, Выпуск: 3-1(93). 2022. –С.52-58.
7. Абдурахманова У.К., Кушиев Х.Х., Жумабаева И.М. Применение моноаммониевой соли глицирризиновой кислоты в качестве биосорбационного реагента на ионы железа (III) Россия. Universum: Химия и биология. Выпуск: 3(81) 2021. 37-42 с.
8. Абдурахманова У.К., Мажидов С.А. Свойства и спектральные характеристики индиго, выделенного из растения «indigofera tinctoria L» Россия, Universum (Химия и биология). -2023. 8(110). –С. 7-41.
9. Маркман А.Л., РжехинВ.П. Госсипол и его производные. М.: Пищ. промыш-т. 1965.- 250 с.
10. У.К.Абдурахманова, М.Р.Аскарлова Аналитические свойства госсипол уксусной кислоты Россия. Универсум: Химия и биология. Выпуск: 12(78) 2020.30-35с.
11. Ugilay K.Abdurahmanova, Khairulla.K.Egamberdiev Adsorption of iron to biologically active substances// Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science 1(1); 2022; - RR.213-219. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7254334>.
12. James A. Kenar Reaction Chemistry of Gossypol and Its Derivatives // JAOCS, -2006. -V. 83. (4). –P.269-302.
13. Adams, R., T.A. Geissman, W.R. Dial, and J.T. Fitzpatrick, Structure of Gossypol. XXVI. Gossypolic Acid, // Ibid. -1941. -Vol. 63. –P.2439–2441.